

Design of a new Workstation in a Productive Process: importance of Multidisciplinary Integration

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Abstract

During the 7th semester of the Integrated Master Degree in Industrial Engineering and Management (IEM) at University of Minho - Portugal, teams of students develop projects in interaction with industry. The project lasts the whole semester and each team works in a different company. This type of projects is formally included in the IEM curricular structure through the course unit (CU) PIEGI2 (Integrated Project in IEM 2) and in fact involves all the remaining five CU of the semester as PSU (Project Supporting Courses). This paper is associated to the work carried out by a team of students in an electrical wiring company (supplier of the automotive industry) and, using qualitative analysis, aims to show the importance of the integration of the contents addressed by the PSUs. Thus, the main goals of this empirical paper are: (i) describe the design process of a new workstation (required due to a problem identified by a customer) and (ii) show how the multidisciplinary integration was important in this project. To design the new workstation, various concepts/tools from the several PSUs were used, namely: (i) anthropometry and illuminance (PSU - Ergonomic Workplace Analysis), (ii) Business Process and Modelling Notation – BPMN (PSU - Integrated Production Management), (iii) Generic Product Data Management – GenPDM (PSU - Production Information Systems), (iv) Value Stream Mapping – VSM and Key Performance Indicators - KPI (PSU - Production Systems Organization II) and (v) SIMIO (PSU - Simulation). By combining contents of all the PSUs of PIEGI2, the students' team was able to develop an integrated solution encompassing not only the physical installation but also managerial aspects (e.g. product data management). Although the new workstation was not yet implemented, the work developed by the students was highly appreciated by the company engineer's and by all the teachers involved.

Keywords: Industry interaction; Active learning; Project-based learning; Multidisciplinary; workstation design

1 Introduction

Industry 4.0, otherwise known as the fourth industrial revolution, is currently attracting the industry attention, in a logic of innovation to ensure competitiveness. This revolution is driven by innovative technologies that have impact in production systems and business models. Industrial companies, namely those in the automotive and machinery sector, are part of a dynamic and highly competitive market, which requires a demand for continuous improvement in production planning, manufacturing processes and operations management. To be competitive, a company must be ahead of technological advances, to respond more efficiently to the increasingly demanding market, with shorter lead times, high quality, reduced cost and diversity.

In many sectors, including the suppliers of the automotive industry, the progressive involvement of customers in the process of developing new products is crucial to ensure the complete alignment of perspectives / requirements. Often, the specific requisites of a new product imply the development of a new production system, or the improvement of existing ones. For this, the design of new production processes may be necessary, eventually involving modified / new equipment (and the respective financial feasibility study), thus constituting a challenge for the company.

This was exactly what happens at the company where the project described in this paper was developed. A specific customer asked for a modification in the products: elimination of the printed identification label affixed to each connector of the electrical wiring and its replacement by the direct printing of the identification code on the connector body. The reason for this customer's request is simple: the label is prone to peel off. Although apparently simple, this modification has major implications, namely in terms of (i) printing process, (ii) supply of materials (connectors) to the assembly line and (iii) wiring assembly process. As for aspects (ii) and (iii), the requested change will increase human error implying thus the development of error-proof mechanisms (poka-

yoke). However, as previously mentioned, this paper addresses aspect (i), i.e., the development of a new workstation with a laser engraving machine to produce connectors with printed identification. Even so, as the new workstation is part of a whole, it is necessary to analyse the entire production process. Naturally, this work (analysis and development) involves the integrated use of different methodologies/techniques/tools, to address aspects such as: ergonomics, process mapping, value stream mapping and product data management, and, at a later stage, production process simulation. In fact, the main purpose of this paper is to emphasize the importance of integration of all these aspects while developing interdisciplinary projects.

As already referred, these projects are developed by teams of students during an entire semester and are based on the Project-Based Learning (PBL) approach (Graaff & Kolmos, 2007; Powell & Weenk, 2003). This kind of projects in interaction with industry is being continuously implemented since 2005 at the Production and Systems Engineering Department of University of Minho, Portugal (Lima et al., 2017).

Thus, in terms of conceptual contribution, this paper aims to contribute to the existing literature on PBL developed in cooperation with industry, by providing evidences of the interdisciplinary integration importance.

The paper is organized as follows. After a brief introduction on chapter 1, chapter 2 presents the theoretical foundation used in the project, namely in terms of lean manufacturing, ergonomics, product data management, process modelling and simulation. The work developed is described in the third chapter and addresses the analysis of the current production process and the development of the new workstation (already mentioning some expected results). The main achievements, problems and conclusions are outlined in chapter 4.

2 Theoretical Foundation

The literature review of an empirical paper should present the underlying theories or the related existing knowledge (Nakano & Muniz, 2018). Thus, this chapter will address the concepts / techniques / tools involved in the project, namely in terms of definition, expected achievements, advantages and disadvantages.

2.1 Lean Tools

Inherent to the lean manufacturing paradigm, there is a large set of methodologies / tools / techniques than can be used both to analyse and improve production systems.

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are measures of system achievements during a given period and are defined accordingly to the intended goal. Organizations use KPIs at multiple levels to evaluate their success.

Value Stream Mapping (VSM) is a graphical tool to represent the material and information flows associated to a product or family of products (Rother & Shook, 2003). A VSM encompasses the entire path taken along the supply chain, from the suppliers to the customer. Like other process mapping methods, it helps in terms of introspection (better understanding of the process), but mainly regarding the analysis / diagnosis and improvement of the process under study.

More specifically, the use of VSM allows (i) the identification of wastes and other problems, which in fact represent improvement opportunities, (ii) the identification of the lean concepts/tools applicable in the analysed context, and (iii) the development of an action plan (eventually a 5W2H plan (what, where, why, who, when, how and how much)) to define and schedule improvement actions.

5S is a widely referred methodology (yet often misunderstood) for organizing spaces so work can be performed efficiently, effectively, and safely. This system focuses on putting everything where it belongs and keeping the workplace clean, which makes it easier for people to do their jobs without wasting time or risking injury. However, the main challenge is to maintain the "5S culture". 5S also facilitate visual control, flow, standard operations and other Just-In-Time (JIT) aspects. The 5S program is usually implemented as a strategic plan for some key aspects of the company to begin to show improvements towards total quality.

2.2 Ergonomic Analysis

From an ergonomic point of view, there are several aspects that may compromise the introduction of a new process/system in a factory. In fact, this is an important area to consider, since it is dealing with the welfare of

the human being. It is still worth mentioning that this topic has an even higher relevance in factories that require a high human work labour, as the employee satisfaction is a key point.

First, ergonomics studies the relation between the human being and the work he executes, seeking to develop an integration between the work conditions, the physical and psychological capacities and limitations of the worker and the efficiency of the productive system. The goal is to increase the safety, health and comfort of the worker, so the workspace adapts to the worker and not the other way around. Indissociable from ergonomics, is anthropometry, which studies the dimensions of various human being parts (using different measuring tools), giving valuable information on the physical and biological conditions of an individual.

Workers performing Manual Material Handling tasks (MMH) are prone to Work-related Musculoskeletal Disorders (WMSD), which are the most frequent occupational health problem in the EU, and MMH is a major cause of vertebral lesions, more specifically in the lumbar region, especially if the materials are heavy and difficult to pick up or handle. When MMH tasks are inevitable, companies should strictly follow the existing legislation to make this task as safe as possible. One of the quantitative methods approached to try to define safe limits is the NIOSH Lifting Equation, or simply NIOSH'91.

Regarding occupational noise, one of the main aspects is the sound pressure, which is expressed in Pascal (Pa). As the human ear reacts logarithmically to stimulation, the sound pressure level scale (logarithmic measure) was created and the unit is the decibel (dB). Noise can cause problems such as loss of audition, reversible lowering of hearing acuity, and destruction of cells. In fact, one third of professional diseases is deafness, resulting from the exposure to high sound levels.

Lighting is an essential factor for a good work environment. Without adequate lighting for the workplace, negative impacts are more likely to happen, either for the health of the worker or for the efficiency of the workplace, resulting in visual damage, an increase in the number of accidents and consequently lower productivity. The lighting provided by natural light is ideal. However, it is not always possible to resort to it, so it is necessary to install artificial light, which can be general, localized or combined.

The fundamental photometric quantity to be taken into consideration is illuminance (E). Illuminance is the measure of the incident luminous flux per unit of surface, measured in lux (lx).

2.3 Product Data Management

"Information systems are interrelated components working together to collect, process, store, and disseminate information to support decision making, coordination, control, analysis, and visualization in an organization." (Laudon & Traver, 2011). There are two different ways of defining information systems: the components that put together an information system and the role that those components take part within an organization. In addition to the obvious components of data, software and hardware, the process and the people are also important components for a system (Boutgeois et al., 2007), as it could not function without them. Focusing on the role that these systems play, it is fair to say that production information systems take an engaging role within the production system of any company (Snehal, n.d.). These systems accelerate the daily pace of actions, change the structure of organizations and shape the essence of work as knowledge and information have grown into vital economic assets (Gutenberg et al., 2017). The versatility to make available different kinds of information at any given time and the ability to provide detailed data (Essays, 2018), is the key factor to an efficient information system. Most organizations depend on external firms to deliver their information services (Gutenberg et al., 2017) as it can be a complex task to achieve a suitable system.

Generic Referencing

In the age of industry 4.0, amongst other requirements for a company to be eligible as a Smart Manufacturing System, it is the capacity to address product diversity and mass customization, which in addition to working to satisfy the exact needs of customers, tries to preserve the gains of mass production (Pine, 1993).

Traditional representation models have fallen short to match up the requirements to deal with the very high diversity of products that characterizes current markets (Gomes et al., 2011; Martins & Sousa, 2013). In this context, the Product Data Management (PDM) function becomes extremely complex, demanding innovative approaches, namely the generic referencing paradigm. Generic referencing seeks to group articles by families,

differentiating them by previously established parameters that facilitate referencing. To obtain a trustworthy information system and being generic referencing one of the main tools to use, it was followed the six-step method introduced in Gomes et al. (2011).

2.4 Process Modelling

Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) allows the representation of business processes by creating a diagram using a set of standard graphical symbols (OMG, 2011). The primary goal of BPMN is to provide a notation that is readily understandable by all business users, from the business analysts that create the initial drafts of the processes, to the technical developers responsible for implementing the technology that will perform those processes, and finally, to the business people who will manage and monitor those processes. With BPMN it is possible to fill the information gap between the conceptual and process implementation.

As for existing processes, BPMN is used to diagnose problems and identify improvement opportunities. However, communication failures are an obstacle to its adoption: it is essential to inform organization employees about the inherent purpose and benefits. Also, the lack of support from management, as well as the lack of knowledge about the model (leading to “fear of change”), always weigh in accepting BPMN use. Financial issues also represent resistance to BPMN utilization. The difficulty in expressing the monetary results obtained with this model, contributes to the scepticism of the managers regarding the return on investment.

2.5 Simulation

In general terms, simulation can be interpreted as the imitation of the operation of a real-world process or system over time (Banks, 1999). According to this author, it is an experimental method with detailed modelling of a real system, where, through visual models’ and/or graphical animation, it is possible to predict how the system will behave in each period of time. In the context of learning environments, Guneri & Seker refer that an abstract computer simulation can be used to represent the essential features of the intended system, so that learners can test their analytical and design skills in a convenient and safe environment.

Among many simulation programs, SIMIO was adopted for this project. It is based on intelligent objects, and unlike other simulation systems, there is no need to write any programming code, as the process is completely graphic (Pegden, 2007; Sturrock & Pegden, 2010). In SIMIO, a vehicle, a customer or any other agent of a system are examples of possible objects and, combining several of these, one can represent the components of the system in analysis. Thus, a SIMIO model may look like the real system.

To create a simulation process, it is needed to identify the problem and formulate it, draw the model, collect data. After that it is crucial to verify and validate the model. If the model is approved then the test plan is next, model execution and results analyses.

SIMIO allows the simulation of various situations that may occur and directly influence the production process. The observation of the material, people or information flows provides a better insight of the process behaviour.

3 Developed Work

In this chapter will be presented the practical application of the techniques referred above.

3.1 Value Stream Mapping and Workplace Organization

The application of some Lean tools in the company where this project was carried out, was extremely useful, as they allowed to understand the current problems and conditions of the production process.

In the assembly lines, various KPI have been measured, such as cycle time, takt time, work in process, setup time or line efficiency. These values allowed to evaluate the current performance of the assembly line and to compare it with the performance of the assembly line after the implementation of the new workstation with the laser engraving machine. This machine will allow four employees to work simultaneously.

VSM was applied in order to identify problems and respective causes (current state VSM). Next, the intention was to develop a future VSM to illustrate what was expected to be achieved with the changes, such as the creation of the new workstation that would in turn change the way the assembly line was supplied. However,

due to time constraints, the future state VSM was not developed. Nevertheless, the current state VSM provided valuable input for the design of the new workstation, namely regarding the previously mentioned KPI.

To create a better working environment in the company, and consistency for high quality processes, the 5S methodology was applied. It was mainly used in areas adjacent to the assembly lines, where there were too many boxes and other components, completely messy and stacked on top of each other. As for the new workstation, an "ideal" layout was developed, however, it was not implemented.

3.2 Noise, Illuminance and Anthropometric Analysis

NIOSH'91 equation will not be implemented in this company, as the tasks performed by the workers do not require the movement of objects.

Companies where lower exposure action values $L (Ex, 8h)$ exceed 80 dB (A) or (c, peak) exceed 135 dB (C), must provide employees with Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) to prevent hearing damage. As the new workstation will be located close to a noise producing source (sectioning area), additional constructive measures to reduce the propagation of noise, such as noise-proof panels, will be necessary.

The analysis of the values provided by the company, revealed that the illuminance in the assembly line was between 300 and 500 lux. ISO 8995:2002 states that illuminance values shall be calculated according to the visual requirements of the task to ensure its proper performance. In addition to this, the costs associated with the lighting system should also been taken into consideration, without affecting optimal energy use. Depending on the tasks, visual requirements range from low to high, ranging from 200 lux to 1000 lux. At the station considered, which was one the assembly lines, the visual demands are high, so a lighting system with a range between 500 and 1000 lux is recommended.

The integration of contents/tools of the PSU Ergonomic Workplace Analysis, made it easier to design an ergonomic workstation, e.g. by defining some important dimensions. Naturally, the worker's satisfaction and welfare at his workstation are quite important in terms of productivity.

3.3 Generic Referencing

The company works with more than 600 electrical wiring references. In order to deal with diversity, the use of the generic referencing concept was proposed. To demonstrate the usefulness of this approach, it was developed the generic PDM model of a cable, a major component of any electrical wiring (Figure).

Figure 1. Generic PDM model of a family of cables.

This model includes the family characterization (upper area), the generic bill-of-materials (lower left area) and the generic bill-of-operations (lower right area). With this approach, instead of being stored in the system, the bill-of-materials and the bill-of-operations of any specific cable are automatically generated only when they are necessary. This is just one of the aspects that shows that the effort associated to PDM is much lower when generic referencing is adopted.

3.4 Failure Recovery Procedure Modelling

When the customized connectors (with the engraved identification code), produced in the new workstation, start to be used in the assembly lines, there will have to be a new procedure to face a specific problem: the need to replace a defective connector. In this scenario, both the employees and the segment leaders need to know how to act. The process was designed and represented with BPMN (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Process for substitution of a defective connector.

This BPMN diagram determines the tasks that each person involved must execute to deal with the referred problem, and, thus, can be interpreted as an alternative way of defining a standard work procedure.

3.5 Material Flow and Production Rate Simulation

To study the material flow from the warehouse to the assembly line, passing through the laser engraving machine, a simulation was created. Thus, in a controlled environment it was possible to understand the impacts of certain variables in the process, e.g. the absence of a worker of the new workstation. The SIMIO technique allows to verify how this absence will influence the production of the laser engraving machine and if this will compromise the supply of the assembly line (by estimating the supply delay time).

After running the simulation and doing some tests, it was concluded that one worker could engrave 8000 connectors in 8 hours, so the new workstation will be able to produce 32000 printed connectors. To supply the four workers of the workstation, it is needed one supplier working for 8 hours too.

4 Conclusion

The design of a new workstation to produce customized electrical connectors, composed by a laser engraving machine and operated by (at most) four workers, was achieved. The development of this workstation implied first the analysis of the entire production process of electrical wiring, which has led to the development of improvement proposals. In the entire project, different aspects were addressed, namely value stream mapping and workplace organization (section 3.1), ergonomic workplace analysis (section 3.2), product data management (section 3.3), process mapping (section 3.4) and simulation (section 3.5). These areas were integrated, to a greater or lesser extent, making it possible to design a workstation with an estimated output of 4000 connectors per hour. One example of such integration occurred between process modelling (PSU - Integrated Production Management) and standard work (PSU - Production Systems Organization II), materialized in the BPMN diagram of Figure 2. Also, the ergonomic design and the 5S methodology worked closely for the workstation development. The layout proposal, for the assembly lines adjacent areas, was developed taking into consideration results coming from simulation. Finally, the work developed in terms of PDM (excerpt represented in Figure), encompassed contents from two PSU: Production Information Systems and Integrated Production Management.

With regard to less successful aspects, it is worth mentioning the case of illuminance and occupational noise, as the students' team had not access to the necessary measuring instruments and, thus, they had to rely on the data provided by the company. Proposals involving noise reduction panels and new lighting systems were developed. However, as the company will be relocated in 2020/2021, the necessary investment is not pertinent.

Unfortunately, it was not possible to implement the new workstation in the period of time allotted for the project. In fact, the only implementation in the shop-floor achieved by the team, was the application of the 5S methodology. However, two important aspects should be mentioned: (i) the feedback from the company regarding the work developed by the students' team was very positive, and (ii) the effective implementation of solutions in the industry, although desirable, is not the primary goal of the PIEGI2 project.

Despite the referred problems, it is clear from above, that the integration of contents from the several PSU was determinant for the project success.

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